

Research

A Quick Aftermath of Dwindling American Economy Due to Corona Pandemic and A Consensus Way-out: Using Statistics and Interpretive Structural Modeling

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Abstract: *The outbreak of the novel Coronavirus has left the entire world stranded in their homes and caused heavy losses to the global economy. The United States have also been highly affected by this pandemic in terms of human life as well as the economic downfall. As the pandemic continues to distort the economy, the researcher has used the technique of interpretive structural modeling to analyze the factors that can help the U.S. get back to its economic strength as it was before the strike of this fatal disease. The researcher has conducted questionnaire based survey with practitioners to identify and filter out the steps that need to be taken for enhancing and saving the economy in the post-virus scenario. After the filtering process the researcher has conducted telephonic interviews with 20 field experts that provided insight to the researcher about the interdependencies of the selected steps. The data from these interviews was then used to create the ISM for this research. The researcher has proposed the consensus way to resolve economic issues through the ISM and has also mentioned the limitations and future research directions for this study.*

Keywords: *Coronavirus, Interpretative Structural Modeling Technique, Economic downfalls, United States, America Economy.*

Introduction

The 2019-2020 coronavirus pandemic has far-reaching consequences beyond the spread of disease and its impact on human lives (McKibbin & Fernando, 2020). In current era, this virus is spreading all over the world which has made a bad impact on the economic development and sustainability of many countries. Many supply chain issues in the international trading decrease the business in

the service sector (Chinazzi et al., 2020). In a similar manner, coronavirus also made a negative impact on the overall economy of the United States, China, and other related countries. There are many cases regarding the shortage of commodities in the lockdown countries due to the panic buying of food, medical supplies and grocery items (Anderson, Heesterbeek, Klinkenberg, & Hollingsworth, 2020). The following figure 1 shows the negative impact of the previous disasters along with COVID-2019 on the capital flow in the global stocks.

Materials and methods

Methodology

In this research the Interpretive Structure Modelling (ISM) approach has been used to explore how the steps recognized through literature for economic revival interact with each other. The ISM approach involves the judgments and decisions from experts that is why this is interpretive technique by nature (Muduli, Govindan, Barve, Kannan, & Geng, 2013). The table 1 given below summarizes the research flow adopted in this study, along with the outcome for each step is given. In the first step, the researcher draws the preliminary steps that need to be taken for improvement of economy by conducting a review of past literature on epidemics and pandemics. In the next step, the researcher conducted a questionnaire survey with the aim of filtering out the most important steps to economic recovery in the U.S. The respondents were selected by using purposive sampling method. In the final step the researcher had to develop the structural model based on ISM technique by analyzing the interrelationships between the identified steps to economic recovery. For this purpose, the researcher has conducted semi-structured telephonic interviews which were later transcribed. These interviews were conducted with 20 industrials which included 7 firm and business heads, 5 heads of government organizations, 5 heads of the NGOs and 3 economists economic professionals belonging to academia and to the business world of the U.S. who become the ultimate expert opinions resources in this research. These experts were responsible for identifying the relationships and interdependencies. These opinions were used to develop the ISM diagraph and model.

Conclusion

This paper has presented a hierarchal framework that can be used as a roadmap to economic recovery after the coronavirus has been dealt with and life is back to normal in the U.S. The study

is novel because these conditions of social distancing and total cut down of inter country transport is unprecedented so the results cannot be compared to previous frameworks and results, however, inspiration has been taken for the formation of factors from previous research regarding disaster management (Benson & Clay, 2003; Jabbour et al., 2017; Patri & Suresh, 2017; Xiao & Nilawar, 2013). The framework results have shown that the first response to disaster needs to be assessment of the damage, so that reformative processes can start. Tax cut down and efficiently managing and distributing the collected donation are outcomes of the risk and damage assessment. These steps lead to several processes which include reducing the tax on exports, introducing flexible work conditions, flow of income and reducing unemployment. These factors lead to stability of the countries socio-economic infrastructure and increased coordination among practitioner which allows formation of accurate strategic plans that can help form long term policies to tackle a similar situation in the future. In short, the consensus way to resolve the economic issues in the U.S. are to assess the damage to economy and then device steps that involve reduction of taxes, improvement of employment ratio, devaluation to increase the buying of local goods and then finally forming a strategic plan that can lead to long term stability of the economy. Moreover, it is highly advised that the countries across the world should develop policies that can help them deal with any future outbreaks of the same nature.

Even though this study has been based on the economic conditions of the U.S., it has global implications because the coronavirus is impacting each and every economy in the world. First of all, this study explains the impact that coronavirus outbreak has on economic structures and then it recognizes factors that can be adopted after the virus has been dealt with so that the economy can bounce back. The framework is applicable to any developed economy, however, reduction of taxes and devaluation has entirely different perspectives in a developing or an underdeveloped country. Therefore, there is scope for the peers to conduct future researches about the impact of coronavirus and how to solve the economic issues in a developing country. Moreover, ISM is a theoretical model and the future researchers should investigate the viability of the framework by conducting analytical and statistical tests.

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